

EFFECT THE USAGE OF AXLE AND SECOND SHIP HELPER ON FISH CAPTURE OF PURSE SEINE FISHERMEN IN BANYUWANGI DISTRICT

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Abstract—This research was done in Banyuwangi District, East Java Province. The purposes are: (1) analyzing the business with axle tool and second ship helper, (2) analyzing the factors affecting the fish capture of purse seine fishermen. This research uses descriptive method. Data is collected by interviews, questionnaires and documentation. The analysis method used is business profits analysis and dummy regression analysis with equation $CR = \hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}_1 SD + \hat{\alpha}_2 CN + \hat{\alpha}_3 FD + \hat{\alpha}_4 FE + \hat{\alpha}_5 EP + \hat{\alpha}_6 SF + \hat{\alpha}_7 GT + \hat{\alpha}_8 D + e^u$. This research is qualitative and quantitative descriptive. Study results are follows: (1) Business to use ship with axle tool can makes money of Rp.184.090.909,00, R/C ratio of 1.58, profit of Rp.66.899.712,00. BEP sales of Rp.21.953.703,00 and BEP units of 4,390 kg. Profitability is 58.49%. Effort analysis for ship by second ship helper can makes money of Rp.306.590.909,00, R/C ratio of 1.60, profit of 115,671,596.00. BEP sales of Rp.28.739.225,00 and BEP unit of 5,747 kg. Profitability is 60.22%. (2) Factors that significantly effect on fishermen catch are the crew number (CN), fishing duration (FD), fishingexperience (FE), enginepower (EP), sail frequency (SF), and Gross tonnage (GT) of ship, while sailing distance does not affect significantly on fish catch.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one country with sea area is larger than the land. Indonesia deserves to be called as a maritime nation. The abundance of fishery resources in Indonesia becomes target for foreign ships with larger engine power and better technology than ship from Indonesia fishermen. The ship of Indonesian fishermen is still relatively traditional. This is because the Indonesian fishermen consider modern ships damage the environment and makes the others fishermen catch reduced (Markandya, and Richardson, 1992). Ships at Bali Muncar strait are classified as large ships although cannot be said as modern ships. The ships have been use axle tools to help the work of crew (ABK). Axle is used by fishermen to pull the rope net faster and more catch result (Wijayanti, N. 2008).

Banyuwangi district is located at eastern tip of East Java province with area of 5782.50 km² and 291.5 km coastline and having large potential of coastal resources and diverse. Banyuwangi has great potential, especially the potential of coastal fisheries.

East coast of Banyuwangi (Bali Strait) is one of largest fish producer in East Java. Therefore, it is necessary to study the potential usage of fishing gear and fishing tools by local fishermen to catch fish (Pemda, 2005)

The catch result of every ship need to be studied, both ships with axle tool and ships with second ship helper. The catch is calculated and compared to know the more efficient and effective ship to operate in area of Bali Muncar strait. This research can be used by local agencies to make rule regarding the two types of ship. It can be viewed and compared from financial aspects. Dummy regression is also used to see the more profitable ship to be used by local fishermen. In this case the fishermen actually can be helped so that they can live more prosperous (Panayotou, 1982).

Fishermen are people who are actively catch the fish. Communities whose livelihood are fishing and spend most of the time at sea are referred as fisherman by surrounding community (Primyastanto *et al.*, 2013b). Their income also only determined by number of fish catch. Welfare level is

determined by income and consumption levels of fishermen (Primyastanto *et al.*, 2013c). Most people around Muncar work as fisherman and also factory workers to meet their needs. Fishermen select the type of sailing ship, both *slerek* or axle types. They must get the fish as much as possible to increase the income (Hilborn and Walters, 1992).

Many fishing capture in Indonesia use *slerek* ships and axle ship. Banyuwangi community often use two *slerek* ship (a ship that helped by second ship) and axle ship with one ship, assisted by towing rope nets tool called axle. *Slerek* ships need more crew and time to pull the rope nets while the axle ship does need lesser crew because it is assisted with axle to pull the rope nets.

Axle ships in Muncar only owned by high income fishermen because the capital needed is hundreds millions rupiah. Ship that helped by second ship (*slerek* type) have greater investment costs because it uses two ships to operate with the capital above 1 milliard. It is a fantastic figure to start a business with both types of ship.

These study purposes are: (1) analyzing the business with axle tool and second ship helper, (2) analyzing the factors affecting the fish capture of purse seine fishermen.

Research Methods

This study uses multiple methods to collect the data as interviews, questionnaires and documentation. Regression analysis is used to analyze business performance. This research is a qualitative and quantitative descriptive. Sample is chosen by simple random sampling, technique to gives an equal opportunity for population to become sample. All samples member in a simple random sampling have homogeneous characteristics that taken randomly or use random table. There are 190 fishermen that chosen randomly 5% presentation to represent population of this study. Thus the number of samples taken in this study is as much as 44 fishermen. The sample is spread across the Muncar harbor. Data is collected from respondents by giving questionnaire and meet with ship owners and marine leader in harbor and around the Kedungrejo village.

Business Profit Analysis

Financial analysis is used by researchers to answer the problem formulation regarding business performance of axle ships and ship with second ship helper (Primyastanto, 2011).

a. Capital

Capital is focused on value, purchasing power, or power to use money or goods.

b. Cost and Revenue (TC and TR)

- Total Revenue (TR)
 $TR = P \times Q$
- Total Cost (TC)
 $TC = FC + VC$

c. Revenue Cost Ratio (R/C ratio)

$$R/C \text{ ratio} = \frac{TR}{TC}$$

The criteria are below:

If the value of $R/C > 1$, then the business is profitable

If the value of $R/C = 1$, then the business is break even

If the value of $R/C < 1$, then the business is loss

d. Profit

According Primyastanto *et al.*, (2005), profit can be formulated as follows:

$$\pi = TR - TC$$

e. Break Even Point (BEP)

1. Based on unit
 $BEP (Q) = FC / (P - VC)$
2. Based on sales
 $BEP (Rp) = FC / (1 - VC/S)$
- f. Rentability
 $RU = (\text{Profit} / \text{Capital}) \times 100\%$

Regression Analysis

Dummy regression analysis used by researchers to solve the problems regarding the factors affecting the catch and to know the effect of towing rope nets tools on fishermen catch. According to Ghazali, I. (2009), in Primyastanto *et al.*, (2012a), factors affecting the fishermen catch based on dummy regression model are as follows:

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SD + \beta_2 CN + \beta_3 FD + \beta_4 FE + \beta_5 EP + \beta_6 SF + \beta_7 GT + \beta_8 D + e^u$$

With following description:

- Y = Capture Results (CR)
- X1 = Sailing Distance (SD)
- X2 = Crew number (CN)
- X3 = Fishing Duration (FD)
- X4 = Fishing Experience (FE)
- X5 = Engine Power (EP)

- X6 = Sail Frequency (SF)
- X7 = GT of ship
- D₁ = 1 ship helped by second ship
- D₁ = 0 Ships with axle tool
- â₀ = Intercept
- â₁₋₈ = coefficient of regression
- eu = Standard Error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Business Performance Analysis

Research results show that business analysis for ship with axle tools produce income of Rp. 184.090.909,00, R/C ratio of 1.58, profit of Rp.66.899.712,00. BEP sales of Rp. 21,953,703.00 and BEP unit of 4,390 kg. Profitability is 58.49%. Business analysis for ship with second boat produces income of Rp.306.590.909,00, R/C ratio of 1.60, profit of 115,671,596.00. BEP sales of Rp.28.739.225,00 and BEP unit of 5,747 kg. Profitability is 60.22%. Performance of ship with axle tools is smaller than ship with second ship. But the overall business performance of both ships types is equally beneficial.

Ship with second ships helper have BEP value of unit and sales are greater than ships with axle tool. BEP calculation above shows that the business is profitable because the value for BEP unit from fish catch is smaller than the total amount of production result. BEP calculation is look at breakeven point of a business. It means that business is not gains and losses at break event point. Therefore this business still feasible for future plan.

Ship with second ships helper have BEP value of unit and sales are greater than ships with axle tool. Below is BEP in graphical for ships with axle tools and a second ship helper:

- BEP with axle tool
- BEP with second ship helper

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis with SPSS 16 is used to know

Fig. 1. Graph of Break Event Point (BEP)

the tools with more favorable catch and estimation factors affecting catch of purse seine fishermen. Research result shows that from all eight (8) independent variables, Sailing distance (X1) does not affect significant, while X2 (Crew number) X3 (Fishing Duration), X4 (Fishing Experience), X5 (Engine Power), X6 (Sail Frequency) and X7 (GT of ship) have significant effect on fish catch.

The constant value is -2.748 with regression coefficient (B) for each variable are 0.150 for X1 (sailing distance), -0.100 for X2 (Crew number), 0.184 for X3 (fishing duration), 0.181 for X4 (fishing experience), 1.272 for X5 (engine power), 0.136 for X6 (sail frequency), 0.375 for X7 (GT of ship) and 0.143 for D variable (dummy). Therefore, the equation can be state as follows:

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SD + \beta_2 CN + \beta_3 FD + \beta_4 FE + \beta_5 EP + \beta_6 SF + \beta_7 GT + \beta_8 D + e^u$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 D + e^u$$

If D = 0 for ship with axle tool, then

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 (0) + e$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + e^u$$

If D = 1 for ship with second ship helper, then

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 (1) + e^u$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 + e^u$$

In this case, the created model can be used to see a catch result comparison between ship with axle tool and ship with second ship helper. The dominant factors to affect fishermen catch are crew number members, fishing duration, fishing experience, engine power, sail frequency, (GT of ship and fishermen with second ship helper. it can be said that addition second ship helper more profitable to increase fish catch. In this case, sailing distance is not included due to insignificant (significance value > 0.05).

R² Test (coefficient of determination)

Table 1 shows that Adjusted R Square value of 0.975. It means that independent variables X1 (Sailing distance), X2 (Crew number) X3 (Fishing Duration), X4 (Fishing Experience), X5 (Engine Power), X6 (Sail Frequency), X7 (GT of ship) and D (ship with second ship helper) simultaneously have significant effect

on fish catch of purse seine fishermen at 97.5%. It can be concluded that capture results of purse seine fishermen is affected at 97.5% by X1 (Sailing distance), X2 (Crew number) X3 (Fishing Duration), X4 (Fishing Experience), X5 (Engine Power), X6 (Sail Frequency), X7 (GT of ship) and D (ship with second ship helper). While other 2.5% is affected by other variables outside the independent variables as weather conditions and others.

2.2.F Test

Table 2 shows that value of F-count is 205.761 at significance level of 0.000. F-table from statistical tables for $df=8$ and residual value=34 is 2.23. It can be seen that value of F count ($205.761 > F$ table (2.23) or significant ($0.00 < \alpha 0.05$).

Therefore, H_0 which state that Sailing distance, Crew number, Fishing Duration, Fishing Experience, Engine Power, Sail Frequency, GT of ship and Dummy of ship with second ship helper do not affect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen is rejected (H_0 rejected), and H_1 which state that Sailing distance, Crew number, Fishing Duration, Fishing Experience, Engine Power, Sail Frequency, GT of ship and Dummy of ship with second ship helper affect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen is accepted (H_1 accepted). It can be concluded that all independent variables of Sailing distance (X1), Crew number (X2), Fishing Duration (X3), Fishing Experience (X4), Engine Power (X5), Sail Frequency (X6), GT of ship (X7) and Dummy (ship with second ship helper) have significant effect on Y (fish catch of purse seine fishermen)

2.3 t test

Above table of data analysis as the output from the analysis of dummy regression model can contribute following conclusion.

Table 1. R² Test value

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std Error of The Estimate	D-W (Durbin-Watson)
1	.990	.980	.975	02034	1.785

Table 2. F test value

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.681	8	.085	205.761	.000
Residual	.014	34	.000		
Total	.695	42			

Effect of sailing distance (X1) on fish catches of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis fishermen show that t count $< t$ -table. It means H_0 is accepted and H_1 rejected, namely sailing distance partially does not have significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fisherman. In according to Fauzan (2011) sailing distance affecton catch quantity of fishermen. Reaching wider fishing area will provide opportunities for fishermen to get more catches.

This study show sailing distance affect insignificantly on fish catch. Sailing distance do not decide the fishermen catch. Muncar fishermen always catch the fish in Bali Strait or the surrounding areas. Therefore, the distance does not have not significant effect to fish catch.

Effect of Crew number(X2) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis shows that value of t count $> t$ -table, therefore H_0 rejected and H_1 accepted. It means the crew number partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Crew number relates to labor availability to catch fish. Bigger size ships usually directly proportional to number of crew and production quantities of fish catches. Crew has significant effect to speed up the process to operate purse seine fishing gear in order to minimize fish opportunity to escape from the open gap (Mukthar, 2008).

This study shows that crew number has significant effect on fish catch. More crew number in a ship can easier and shortens operation time to operate fishing gear (Rachman *et al.*, 2013)

Effect of fishing duration (X3) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis shows that value of t count $> t$ -table, therefore H_0 rejected and H_1 accepted. It

means fishing duration partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Theoretically, number of day’s operation also has a positive effect on catch/production of fisherman. Longer days at sea will provide larger total catches. Fishing ships are required to operate with a longer time, because open water need more time to hunt fish and move based on season (Primyastanto *et al.*, 2014).

Muncar Fishermen do not require many days at sea. It takes just 24 hours, from left up to return to port and directly sell their fish, so does not add to operational costs such as ice cubes and also diesel fuel (Primyastanto, 2012a).

Effect of fishing experience (X4) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis shows that value of t count > t-table, therefore H0 rejected and H1 accepted. It means partially fishing experience has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Theoretically, experience factor is not discussed in book discusses for income or profits function. But in practice, more experienced fishermen can increase their catch at sea and also meaning to increase the income (Sujarno, 2008).

Muncar fishermen have experience to go to sea. They do not need modern tools to determine fish location. They search manually by using a lifeboat and will soon find out the fish location (Zain, Johnny *et al.*, 2009).

Effect of engine power (X5) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis show that value of t count > t-table, therefore H0 rejected and H1 accepted. It means that

engine power partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Theoretically, engine power will determine the speed of ship to hunt fish and encircling purse seine tools to the moving fish. Ships with high speed can impede or compete with fish speed. Therefore, faster ship than fish will increase the chances to catch fish cluster. With large engine power engine, the process to encircle fish cluster will faster and fish chances to escape also smaller (Iskandar Dahri and Ade Guntur, 2014)

Engine power is very exploited by Muncar fishermen to quickly arrive at fish location and also take advantage of engine power to pull the rope net to shorten the time (Habibie, 2010).

Effect of sail frequency (X6) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis show that value of t count > t-table, therefore H0 rejected and H1 accepted. It means that sail frequency partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. It is because a purse seine is operated in Bali Strait, where that location has many fish species that became the livelihood of fishermen. Whenever fishermen go to sail, they will get fish though the amount is small or different. Therefore, higher frequency of fishing operations can increase opportunity to get fish (Primyastanto *et al.*, 2013a).

Muncar fisherman catches fish by seeing sea and weather conditions. If the weather is bad or conditions is not conducive, the fishermen will remain on land and not take the risk to go to sea (Heryansyah, 2013).

Effect of GT ship (X7) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis show that value of t count > t-table,

Table 3. Value of t test

Variabel	t-count	t-table	Sig.	Description
Sailing distance (X1)	1.084	1.690	.286	NS
Crew number (X2)	-2.948	1.690	.006	***
Fishing Duration (X3)	2.482	1.690	.019	**
Fishing Experience (X4)	3.144	1.690	.003	***
Engine Power (X5)	8.816	1.690	.000	***
Sail Frequency (X6)	3.418	1.690	.002	***
GT of ship (X7)	4.452	1.690	.000	***
Dummy (D)	8.512	1.690	.000	***

Description:
 ***: Significant at 99% level
 **: Significant at 95% level
 *: Significant at 90% level
 NS: Non Significant

therefore H0 rejected and H1 accepted. It means that GT ship partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Greater shipsize (GT) will affecton catches capacity, fishing gear, and crews in fishing operations (Sulandari, 2011).

GT shipranges in Muncar are from 10 to 30 GT. The greater GT ship will also increase the fish catch, because greater GT ship can reach wider area then this makes the opportunity to get the catch even more (Primyastanto *et al.*, 2012b).

Effect of dummy variables (ship with tools second helper) on fish catch of purse seine fishermen

Partial analysis show that value of t count > t-table, therefore H0 rejected and H1 accepted. It means that dummy variable (ship with second ship helper) partially has significant effect on fish catch of purse seine fishermen. Ship with second ship helper catch more fish than the ship with axle tool (Nova *et al.*, 2015).

Conclusions and Suggestions

CONCLUSION

The conclusions from this study are below.

1. Analysis of fish catches business of purse seine fishermen

• With axle tool

Ship with axle tools is quite favorable as seen from income of Rp.184.090.909 per month and R/C ratio of 1.58 for 1 month. Profit of Rp.66.899.712 per month shows the BEP sales is Rp.21.953.703per month. BEP values for a unit of fishing effort is of 4,390 Kg per month. The business profitability value is 58.49%.

• Ships With Aid Ships Second

Ship with second shiphelper produces income of Rp.1.306.590.909 per month and R/C ratio of 1.60 for per month. At profit of Rp.115.671.596 per month, the BEP sales is Rp.28.739.225per month. BEP values for a unit of fishing effort is of 5,747 Kg per month. The business profitability is 60.22%. Therefore, fishing business of purse seine fishermen with second shiphelper is more profitable than ship with axle tool.

2. Regression Analysis

Dummy regression analysis produces following equation:

The equation can be state as follows:

$$CR = \hat{\alpha}_0 + \hat{\alpha}_1 SD + \hat{\alpha}_2 CN + \hat{\alpha}_3 FD + \hat{\alpha}_4 FE + \hat{\alpha}_5 EP + \hat{\alpha}_6 SF + \hat{\alpha}_7 GT + \hat{\alpha}_8 D + e^u$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 D + e$$

If D = 0 for ship with axle tool, then

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 (0) + e^u$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + e^u$$

If D = 1 for ship with second ship helper, then

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 (1) + e^u$$

$$CR = -2,748 + 0,150 SD - 0,100 CN + 0,184 FD + 0,181 FE + 1,272 EP + 0,136 SF + 0,375 GT + 0,143 + e^u$$

Above equations show that ship with second ship helper will increase fish catch at 0.143. Ship with axle tool will not increase fish catch of fishermen. In this case, the created model can be used to see a comparison between ship with axle tool and ship with second ship helper towards fishermen catch. The factors that most affecton fishermen catch are Sailing distance, Crew number, Fishing Duration, Fishing Experience, Engine Power, Sail Frequency, and GT of ship and Dummy of ship with second ship helper. In this case the sailing distance sail is not included due to insignificant (significance value > 0.05).

Suggestion

Suggestions from this study are below.

1. Investment should be utilized maximally in order to maximize its advantages. Investments with a second ship helper are higher but the profits were also higher so fishermen is more advisable to use a ship with second ship helper.
2. Sailing distance should be more concerned. Fishermen can look for another fishing area to improve their fish catch. Sailing distance affect insignificant because the fishing area at Muncar always located in same location so that catch area needs to be expanded further.
3. For government, namely Department of Marine and Fisheries need should makes socialization, mentoring and supervision in order fishermen would use more modern tool to catch fish to get more result and shorter time to find the fish

location to reduce operating costs such as diesel, gasoline and ice cubes.

4. The academics should further research the factors affecting the fish catch with other tools to tow the rope nets.

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